

On the Proteinase in the Milky Juice of *Calotropis Gigantea*. Its Purification and Activation by Ascorbic Acid and Glutathione.

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Basu and Nath (*J. Indian Chem. Soc. Ser. P. C. Ray Comm. Vol. 1933, p. 107*) have already reported on the occurrence of a proteolytic enzyme in the milky juice of *Calotropis gigantea*. The enzyme, it was shown, could hydrolyse gelatine, casein, egg-albumin, and fibrin and its optimum p_H was 5.0. The juice was shown to contain a natural activator whose amount diminished as the plant grew older. Sulphuretted hydrogen, cysteine, and also hydrocyanic acid were found to exert an activating influence on the enzyme. The investigation has been continued with special reference to the purification and activation of the enzyme.

EXPERIMENTAL

The proteolytic activity was measured by titration with alcoholic potash solution from a micro-burette. Contrary to our previous result it has been found that the enzyme, both in presence of the natural activator as well as in presence of sulphuretted hydrogen, can hydrolyse peptone. Table I makes it clear.

TABLE I.

10 C.c. of 2% Witte peptone solution at p_H 5.0, 1 c.c. citrate buffer and the clear centrifugate from 1 c.c. juice, made up to 25 c.c. and 5 c.c. titrated. Temp. = 40°.

Activator	Hydrolysis (0.023 N-KOH).	
	After 1 hr.	After 3 hrs.
...	1.3 c.c.	1.8 c.c.
H ₂ S	1.52	2.0

The juice was found to contain no dipeptidase and very little polypeptidase. In the milky juice of *Calotropis gigantea* only one enzyme, which appears to be very similar to papain, is responsible for hydrolysing the proteins to amino-acids. This observation is contrary to the view of Vines ("The Proteins of Plants," London, 1930) who holds that there are two proteases in plants viz., (i) the peptase that hydrolyses protein molecules to peptones, and (ii) the creptase that hydrolyses the

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peptones formed, to amino-acids, but supports the views of Willstätter (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, **138**, 184; 1926, **153**, 250).

Purification.

That the enzyme is present in the water soluble part of the juice is evident from Table II.

TABLE II.

Substrate—gelatine; 5 c.c. of 5% gelatine solution at p_H 5; 1 c.c. citrate buffer of p_H 5; Clear centrifugate from 1 c.c. juice made up to 25 c.c. and 5 c.c. titrated. Temp. 40°. (Sample of juice—B)

Hydrolysis (0.023N-KOH) after 1 hr.		
With 1 c.c. fresh juice.	With clear centrifugate from 1 c.c. juice.	With water insoluble portion from 1 c.c. juice.
1.33 c.c.	1.95 c.c.	0 c.c.

Attempts to purify the enzyme by precipitation of the aqueous solution with alcohol, lead acetate, or mercuric sulphate were not successful and resulted in the precipitation of inactive products. The residue obtained by treating the solid obtained by drying in juice in vacuum at the ordinary temperature with ether and acetone and also glycerine extract of the juice (dried in vacuum) were without any proteolytic activity.

In order to obtain the enzyme in a more active state, 100 c. c. of the juice were diluted with water and centrifuged. The clear liquid (650 c. c.) was divided into 5 fractions and each fraction treated in different manner.

(a) *First fraction.*—100 C. c. of the solution were made half saturated with ammonium sulphate, precipitate dialysed for 4 days in distilled water, later tested for proteolytic activity.

(b) *Second fraction.*—Filtrate from (a) was made full saturated with ammonium sulphate, precipitate dialysed and activity tested for.

(c) *Third fraction.*—100 C. c. were made 0.03 saturated with ammonium sulphate and dilute HCl was added, precipitate dialysed and activity studied.

(d) *Fourth fraction.*—100 C. c. of the solution were acidified with 2 c. c. of strong HCl, precipitate dialysed and proteolytic activity studied.

(e) *Fifth fraction.*—Activity was tested after simply dialysing 100 c. c. of the solution.

The following table shows the results.

TABLE III.

Substrate—gelatine. Activator- H_2S . $p_n = 5.0$. Temp. = 40° .
Procedure same as in Table II.

Method of treatment.	Wt. of solid (equivalent to 1 c.c. juice).	Hydrolysis (0.023N-KOH) after	
		1 hr.	1 hr. per 0.1573 g. solid.
Centrifuged only	0.1573	2.35 c.c.	2.35 c.c.
(a) Centrifuged and half-saturated with ammonium sulphate and dialysed	0.0058	0.3	8.21
(b) Full saturated with ammonium sulphate and dialysed			
(c) 0.03 saturated with ammonium sulphate and acidified with HCl (dilute) and dialysed	0.0097	0.9	14.58
	0.0056	Nil	Nil
(d) Acidified with HCl (strong) and dialysed	0.0041	Nil	Nil
(e) Dialysed after centrifuging	0.011	1.95	27.92

In determining the weight of solid equivalent to 1 c.c. juice, evaporations were, in all the above cases, done in vacuum at the ordinary temperature.

It will be evident from Table III that simple dialysis of the clear centrifugate from the juice yields the most active preparation. The precipitate obtained on half saturating the clear centrifugate with ammonium sulphate is only half as active as the precipitate obtained later on full saturation. The enzyme thus appears to be associated with a protein of the nature of albumin.

We have made a comparative study of the behaviour of calotropis proteinase and papain. The results obtained with fresh juice of both the plants are indicated in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Treatment.	Calotropis proteinase.	Papain.
(1) Precipitation of the aq. extract with alcohol	Ppt. inactive	Ppt. active
(2) Application of heat to the aq. extract	Not coagulable by heat	Coagulable at about 80°
(3) (a) Half of the aq. extract saturation with am. sulphate (b) Full saturation of the remaining mother-liq.	Ppt. active Do	No ppt. Ppt. active
(4) Effect of H-ion conc. on the solubility of the enzyme	Insoluble at pH lower than five and in dilute alkali	Same as in former

Activation.—It has previously been shown that reducing agents like HCN, H₂S and cysteine are capable of activating the enzyme, and that natural activators are present in the juice, specially of younger plants. The problem is to find out the nature of this natural activator. Ascorbic acid and glutathione are constituents of many plants and it would be interesting to see whether these two substances are present in the juice and whether they have got any activating action on the proteolytic enzyme present in the juice.

Glutathione, ascorbic acid and cysteine in the juice were determined as follows. Titration with iodine solution (*cf.* Tunnicliffe, *Biochem. J.*, 1925, **19**, 194) gave the equivalent of all these three substances provided they were the only reducing substances present. The juice was then titrated with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol according to the method of Birch, Harris and Ray (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, **27**, 580), Harris and Ray (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, **27**, 303). Another titration with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol after removing cysteine as recommended by Emmerie (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, **28**, 268, 1153) gave the amounts of ascorbic acid and cysteine. Table V indicates the results.

TABLE V.

Titration with iodine soln.	Titration with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol.	Titration with the indicator after removal of cysteine with mercuric acetate
2 C.c. I ₂ soln. containing 2.48 mg. I ₂ .	5 C.c. of the indicator soln.	1 C.c. indicator soln.
∩ 9.10 c.c. of dil. juice.	∩ 0.595 mg. I ₂ .	∩ 3.5 c.c. of diluted juice.
∩ 1.02 c.c. of original juice.	∩ 7.8 c.c. of dil. juice.	∩ 0.392 c.c. of original juice.
Hence 1. c.c. of juice ∩ 2.432 mg. iodine.	∩ 0.374 c.c. of original juice.	Hence ascorbic acid in 1 c.c. juice ∩ 0.304 mg. iodine.
	Hence ascorbic acid and cysteine in 1 c.c. juice ∩ 0.68 mg. iodine.	

Thus the calotropis juice contains per c.c. (if other reducing agents are assumed to be absent), 2.094 mg. glutathione, 0.211 mg. ascorbic acid and 0.180 mg. cysteine. An attempt was made to isolate the glutathione by the method of Hopkins (*J. Biochem.*, 1929, **84**, 269) but although a white cuprous salt was obtained with cuprous oxide we could ultimately isolate only oxalic acid.

The activating effect of ascorbic acid, ascorbic acid-Fe⁺⁺ complex and of glutathione on the calotropis proteinase was then investigated. Parallel experiments were performed with papain as well. Two preparations of the latter were employed. In the first case the fresh juice from *Carica papaya* was extracted by standing overnight in the refrigerator with water. Secondly this aqueous extract was precipitated with alcohol. The calotropis enzyme was employed in the form of clear centrifugate of one c.c. juice. The results are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Substrate—gelatine. p_H , 4.95. Temp. 40°. Procedure same as in Table II.

With clear centrifugate equivalent to 1 c.c. juice used.

Activator.	From <i>Calotropis gigantea</i>		From <i>Carica papaya</i> .		With solid papain (40 mg.)	
	Hydrolysis (in c.c. of 0.23N-KOH) after					
	1 hr.	3 hrs.	1 hr.	3 hrs.	1 hr.	3 hrs.
...	0.60	0.70	1.75	2.50	1.05	1.30
H ₂ S	1.95	2.35	2.30	3.45	1.60	2.25
Glutathione (2.5 mg.)	1.90	2.40	2.20	3.30	1.85	2.35
Ascorbic acid (7 mg.)	1.75	1.85	2.05	3.10	0.90	1.15
Ascorbic acid (7 mg.) with FeSO ₄ (20 mg.)	1.80	1.95	1.80	2.35	1.55	2.00

It will be seen from the Table VI that the aqueous extract of the enzyme from the fresh juice of *Calotropis gigantea* and *Carica papaya* behave very similar towards glutathione and ascorbic acid. Both glutathione and ascorbic acid act as activators and addition of ferrous iron does not increase the activating effect of ascorbic acid; indeed, in the case of juice from *Carica papaya*, iron seems to exert an inhibiting effect. The case is different with the solid preparation of papain

obtained with alcohol. In this case ascorbic acid alone exerts no activating influence; it has on the other hand a slight retarding effect, but ascorbic acid together with iron acts as an activator. Similar result was obtained by Marchmann and Helmert (*Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1934, **223**, 127), who found that the gelatine-splitting power of Merck's papain was inhibited by ascorbic acid, but activated by ascorbic acid plus iron. Putt (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, **29**, 13), has recently observed that ascorbic acid alone cannot, but ascorbic acid-Fe⁺⁺ complex can activate Merck's papain but neither can activate papain rendered inactive by hydrogen peroxide.

SUMMARY.

1. The proteinase in the milky juice of *Calotropis gigantea* which can hydrolyse geiatine, casein, fibrin, and egg-albumin (pH optimum = 5) can also hydrolyse peptone when activated.

2. The enzyme is soluble in water but treatment of the aqueous solution with alcohol, lead acetate or mercuric sulphate results in the formation of an inactive precipitate.

3. Both half-saturation and subsequent full saturation of the aqueous solution yield active precipitates, the latter being more active.

4. Simple dialysis of the solution results in the highest degree of purification of the enzyme.

5. Glutathione, ascorbic acid and cysteine appear to be present in the milky juice.

6. The enzyme in the clear centrifugate of the juice is activated by glutathione and by ascorbic acid. Ferrous iron does not increase the activating power of ascorbic acid. Similar results were obtained with aqueous extract of fresh *Carica papaya* juice.

7. Papain (obtained by precipitation with alcohol, from the fresh juice) is very slightly inhibited in its action by ascorbic acid but accelerated by ascorbic acid-Fe⁺⁺ complex.

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